
Libraries and ChatGPT: A Comparative Study of Relevance, Benefits, and User Attitudes

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Abstract

This study explores the benefits of ChatGPT in academic settings and assesses perceptions among faculty members and postgraduate students regarding traditional libraries versus ChatGPT's capabilities. A quantitative methodology was employed, utilising structured questionnaires to gather data from 138 participants in higher education institutions in Kerala. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Version 21, focusing on descriptive statistics and the Chi-square test. Findings indicate that both students and faculty find ChatGPT advantageous primarily for its accessibility and time-saving features. This study highlights changing user expectations and suggests that library professionals could innovate library services in response, marking a significant examination of library users' perceptions of ChatGPT and the library's role in delivering reliable information to educators and students.

Keywords

ChatGPT, artificial intelligence, chatbots, libraries, librarianship.

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Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is widely applied in many areas of our social life. When machines are made to think and work like human being we call it ‘artificial intelligence. AI is designed to perform all activities that require human intelligence, including learning, problem-solving, and decision-making. There are two systems of artificial intelligence. They are ‘Narrow AI’ and general AI. An AI that is made to do one thing or a specific task ie. Facial recognition and recommendation systems can be recognised as ‘Narrow AI’. ‘General AI’ is that which can perform all the mental tasks, including cognitive ability, adaptability, general problem-solving, and self-improvement. Artificial intelligence uses various methods like machine learning, neural networks and deep learning to analyse datasets and make effective decisions. Machine learning teaches how to learn from the data. Deep learning is a more advanced form of machine learning that uses neural networks to analyse large-scale datasets.

ChatGPT is an advanced large language model (LLM) developed by OpenAI and officially introduced to the public in late November 2022. Different types of deep learning techniques are used to generate relevant text in response to user queries. OpenAI continues to update with current information. ChatGPT helps us to interact with the computers in more conversational way. It aims to reduce the gaps in interaction between humans and machines. The acronym GPT stands for Generative Pre-trained Transformer, referring to a suite of sophisticated natural language models developed by OpenAI to push the boundaries of artificial intelligence in language processing. (Sabzalieva, Emma; Valentini, 2023). ChatGPT offers a range of applications across various fields, including teaching, learning, research, administration, community engagement, technical communication, research design, data collection, data analysis, writing, and more. However, its usage also presents several challenges. These challenges encompass issues related to academic integrity, privacy concerns, cognitive bias, gender and diversity matters, accessibility, and commercialisation.

ChatGPT and Libraries

The emergence of advanced AI tools like ChatGPT presents both opportunities and challenges for academic libraries and information-related professions. These technologies will influence

different aspect of library services, including content creation and information retrieval. These tools will be helpful for literature reviews, creating quick summaries, and guiding to relevant resources. Higher levels of critical evaluation and guidance are required in the new situation. The integration of artificial intelligence raises important questions about the future roles of libraries and librarians, as well as the nature of information literacy. As AI applied systems become effective in performing routine jobs, librarians will have to redefine their traditional roles. The new emerging situation required core competencies of AI literacy, data ethics and information evaluation techniques. Libraries must be relocated as education hubs for AI and its ethical use, developing critical thinking skills among people. These technologies will enhance rather than replace the human expertise and personalized services from academic libraries.

Literature review

Many studies have been published on the use of ChatGPT and similar AI chatbots.

The technological characteristics, its applications, and history of ChatGPT development have been the main theme of some studies. Fernandez (2023) and Zhao et al. (2023) have explained the evolution of chatbots, emphasising their increasing capacities and the variety of applications. According to Pierre-Robertson (2023) and Cox and Tzoc (2023), integrating ChatGPT into library activities has been helpful for staff and users, as it can improve productivity in daily tasks. However, the studies highlight its limitations, such as the chatbot's lack of true understanding and its inability to think critically, raising concerns about its potential over-reliance in the educational context.

Impact on Scholarly Libraries is also a theme in the literature. Research on responses to the use of AI chatbots in academic libraries has been conducted. The basic worry about replacing human staff remains. The fact that it is widely acknowledged that AI may improve response times and service quality (Houston & Corrado, 2023; Mali & Deshmukh, 2023) is true. According to Kendrick (2022) and Adetayo (2023), Aithal and Aithal (2023) AI chatbots should be viewed as supplemental tools rather than as a replacement for the crucial human element in libraries. One important topic that deserves attention is the problem of job displacement and the evolution of the traditional library position. Different

applications of AI tools in libraries are emerging. One among them is the GPT Plugin. Studies have examined its impact on language processing in library systems (Panda & Kaur, 2023). A qualitative research study was performed on 'Aisha', a library chatbot (Lappalainen & Narayanan, 2023). A basic evaluation of ChatGPT was conducted using library reference prompts and article writing prompts (Chen, 2023).

Education's potential and difficulties of ChatGPT are presented in many studies. ChatGPT provides significant educational benefits, particularly in research. According to Subaveerapandiyani et al. (2023), ChatGPT may be a useful tool for teachers and students, supporting academic writing and content creation. But in-depth field research shows that AI-generated content might undermine students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The students who use the technologies excessively may become overdependent on them, which will affect their intellectual development. Concerns regarding uniqueness and authenticity of the content generated by the tools are under research. Kirtania and Patra (2023) mention that originality of the content is important in the academic context. Similarly, the index of AI-generated content needs close examination. These raise issues related to academic integrity. Dong (2024) and George Pallivathukul et al. (2024) studied on influence of ChatGPT. There have been significant variations by age, academic discipline, and geographic location. While some students responded that it is a useful tool, the study highlights a serious need for a deep understanding of ChatGPT and its use. (Abdaljaleel, 2024; Masa'deh et al., 2024)

ChatGPT influences students' learning and the relationship between students' creativity and academic achievement. According to some studies (Padhiyar & Modha, 2024; Silvestre et al., 2024), ChatGPT fosters creativity by giving students new approaches to idea generation and problem-solving skills, and argues that depending too much on AI to create content could limit students' ability to think critically and to engage deeply with academic subjects. It is important to recognise that while ChatGPT may offer quick answers, it cannot replace the deep comprehension and originality that come from independent thought.

Objectives of the study

The Objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To identify the benefits derived from ChatGPT usage among faculty members and postgraduate students.
2. Find out the attitude on the relevance of libraries than ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students
3. Find out the relevance of the library and information system other than ChatGPT

Hypothesis

Three hypotheses are used in the study.

H1: There is a significant difference in the benefits derived from ChatGPT usage among faculty members and postgraduate students.

H2: There is a significant difference in the attitude towards the relevance of libraries than ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students.

H3: There is a significant difference in the attitude toward the Relevance of the library than ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students.

Methodology

The scope of the study is confined to the postgraduate students and teachers of colleges affiliated to University of Kerala, India. There are 151 colleges affiliated with the University of Kerala. The colleges are spread in 4 districts of Kerala, ie. Trivandrum, Kollam, Pathanamthitta and Alappuzha. Data were collected from 4 colleges in these 4 districts. Multi stage sampling technique was adopted to select samples. Structured questionnaires were administered to collect quantitative data, questionnaires were distributed to the teachers and students. 90 post-graduate students and 48 teachers responded. To assess regularity of ChatGPT usage, a 5-point Likert scale was used to ask participants to indicate their agreement with a statement about whether they strongly agree or strongly disagree with ChatGPT.

Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics were conducted on quantitative data and statistical techniques such as the independent sample t test, Pearson correlation and significance were also used. IBM SPSS Version 23 was used for the quantitative data analysis

Results

1. **Benefits of ChatGPT usage among faculty members and postgraduate students.**

Table 1: Benefits of using ChatGPT

Benefit	Respos es	Percenta ge
Save time	84	61
Retrieve information easily	68	49
Easy accessible	97	70
Availability	60	43
User friendliness	59	43

Easy accessibility is the most frequently mentioned benefit, reported by 70% of respondents (97), suggesting that users place a high value on being able to access the tool whenever needed. The next most common response, with 61% (84) of respondents, is saving time, indicating that ChatGPT is well-liked for its ability to accelerate tasks. Other noteworthy advantages include the tool's availability and user-friendliness (reported by 43% of respondents) and the ease of retrieving information (reported by 49%). These findings imply that although users find ChatGPT useful in a variety of ways, the two main advantages that improve the user experience overall are accessibility and time savings.

H1: There is a significant difference in the benefits gained from ChatGPT usage among faculty members and postgraduate students.

Table 2: Comparison of benefits of using ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students.

	Benefit	Sig	Decision
Position	Save time	0.41	Not supported
	Retrieve information easily	0.12	Not supported
	Easy accessible	0.91	Not supported
	Availability	0.30	Not supported
	User friendliness	0.10	Not supported

The above table shows that the benefits of using ChatGPT are similar among faculty members and postgraduate students, as the p-values are greater than 0.05 in all cases.

2. **Attitude on the relevance of libraries compared to ChatGPT, among faculty members and postgraduate students**

H2: There is a significant difference in the attitude toward the relevance of libraries compared to

ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics on the relevance of libraries compared to ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students.

Position * Relevance of library Cross tabulation			Relevance_of_Library		Total
			Relevant	Not Relevant	
Position	Faculty Member	Count	35	13	48
		within Position(percentage)	72.9%	27.1%	100.0%
		Within Relevance_of_library	35.0%	34.2%	34.8%
		Percentage of Total	25.4%	9.4%	34.8%
	Postgraduate students	Count	65	25	90
		Percentage within Position	72.2%	27.8%	100.0%
		Percentage within Relevance of_library	65.0%	65.8%	65.2%
		Percentage of Total	47.1%	18.1%	65.2%
Total	Count	100	38	138	
	Percentage within Position	72.5%	27.5%	100.0%	
	Percentage within Relevance_of_library	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Percentage of Total	72.5%	27.5%	100.0%	

Post graduate students are more likely to find libraries as more relevant (65%) compared to faculty members (35%). Both groups have a similar percentage of relevance (around 72%) within their respective positions.

Table 4: Chi square table

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance(2ided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.008 ^a	1	0.931

The chi-square table shows that the p-value (0.931) is greater than 0.05, thus the difference in the attitude of relevance of libraries than ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students is not significant.

3. Relevance of the Library over ChatGPT

Table 5: Relevance of the Library over ChatGPT

Benefit	Responses	Percentage
In-depth knowledge	74	54
Authentic information	59	43
Credible information	35	25
Reliable information	37	27

54% of respondents (74) stated that the library's capacity to offer in-depth knowledge is its most often mentioned advantage. This implies that patrons still view the library as an important source of comprehensive knowledge, particularly for difficult or scholarly subjects.

Recognised by 43% (59 respondents) as another important library strength, authentic information demonstrates confidence in the uniqueness and correctness of library materials. Though not always for highly vetted or academic content, fewer respondents name trustworthy information (25%) and reliable information (27%) as key advantages. This could reflect growing confidence in digital tools like ChatGPT for easy access.

H3: There is a significant difference in the attitude toward the Relevance of the library than ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students.

Table 6: Comparison of the relevance of the library with ChatGPT among faculty members and postgraduate students.

	Relevance	Sig	Decision
Position	In-depth knowledge	0.326	Not supported
	Authentic information	0.048	Supported
	Credible information	0.630	Not supported
	Reliable information	0.096	Not supported

Only one of the four relevant factors examined reveals a difference between the two groups that is statistically significant:

Trustworthy data ($p = 0.048$): This is corroborated, suggesting that postgraduate students and faculty members have quite different opinions about the library's capacity to deliver reliable information. It implies that one group (possibly faculty) values the authenticity of the 'library resources' more than students do.

There is no statistically significant difference in how faculty and students value the factors, such as in-depth knowledge ($p = 0.326$), credible information ($p = 0.630$), and reliable information ($p = 0.096$). Even though "reliable information" is getting close to significance, it still falls short of the typical cutoff point ($p < 0.05$).

Discussions

Why do people use AI tools like ChatGPT, and what benefits do they have? The study tries to find out the answer. Accessibility is the main factor that attracts them to use it. ChatGPT is easily accessible. Users can save time during searching for information. There are other factors that induce them to use chatGPT is for the easy retrieval of information and user friendliness. The accessibility of ChatGPT is the most important factor that contributes to the wider adoption of it. Additionally, features such as easy information retrieval that allow users to obtain relevant answers without navigating multiple sources or a complex search process can be provided by ChatGPT.

The 4th librarian future report reveals critical gaps and opportunities in how librarians can lead on AI integration in higher education (New Technology from Sage Report Explores Librarian Leadership in the Age of AI, May 2025). In the age of artificial intelligence, getting answers for questions. Is the library relevant in this age? The study shows libraries still hold significant roles. Libraries can provide authentic information. It is reliable. It provides a curated collection, expert guidance, and access to a wide range of physical and digital resources that may not be accessible through AI systems. The study underlines the argument that libraries in the digital age has importance, a balanced approach to information seeking combining the benefits of AI tools with depth research methods. The most frequently mentioned advantage of a modern library system is in-depth knowledge.

The library patron still views the library as an important source of knowledge. A vital strength of

the library is its authentic source of knowledge. Libraries remain valuable even today by offering a wealth of in-depth knowledge. People trust library as a reliable source of information. These strengths highlight the continued importance of libraries as a trustworthy source of information for people.

Conclusion

The study explains the relevance, benefit and user attitude of libraries and chatGPT. The factors that induce them to use it are explained ie. Accessibility, easily retrieval of information, and user friendliness. The study reminds us that libraries remain relevant in the era of AI.

Modern libraries offer in-depth knowledge is a major advance. Another significant merit of libraries is that they provide reliable knowledge. The library's key strength is that it provides authentic information and demonstrates confidence in the uniqueness and accuracy of its resources. However, libraries must adapt to the changing user needs by providing innovative services.

There are limitations in this study, including the sample size and demographics such as gender, social class, and educational qualifications. More in-depth studies are required to determine with precision which library systems and services are needed. The study shows that we need to redesign the libraries. By embracing emerging technologies and fostering an environment that encourages critical thinking and creativity, libraries can remain relevant and vital in the 21st century. This evolution requires librarians to continuously update their skills and knowledge, ensuring they can effectively leverage new tools and methodologies to meet the evolving needs of their communities.

References

- 1) Abdaljaleel, M. *et al.* (2024) 'A multinational study on the factors influencing university students' attitudes and usage of ChatGPT', *Scientific Reports*, 14(1). doi: 10.1038/s41598-024-52549-8.
- 2) Adetayo, A. J. (2023) 'ChatGPT and Librarians for Reference Consultations', *Internet Reference Services Quarterly*. doi: 10.1080/10875301.2023.2203681.
- 3) Aithal, S. and Aithal, P. S. (2023) 'Effects of AI-Based ChatGPT on Higher Education Libraries', *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 8(2), pp. 95–108. doi:

- 10.2139/ssrn.4453581.
- 4) Chen, X. (2023) 'ChatGPT and Its Possible Impact on Library Reference Services', *Internet Reference Services Quarterly*, 27(2). doi: 10.1080/10875301.2023.2181262.
 - 5) Cox, C. and Tzoc, E. (2023) 'ChatGPT Implications for academic libraries', *College and Research Libraries News*, 84(3). doi: 10.5860/crln.84.3.99.
 - 6) Das, S. R. and J.V., M. (2024) 'Perceptions of Higher Education Students towards ChatGPT Usage', *International Journal of Technology in Education*, 7(1). doi: 10.46328/ijte.583.
 - 7) Dong, L. (2024) "'Brave New World" or not?: A mixed-methods study of the relationship between second language writing learners' perceptions of ChatGPT, behaviors of using ChatGPT, and writing proficiency', *Current Psychology*, 43(21). doi: 10.1007/s12144-024-05728-9.
 - 8) Fernandez, P. (2023) "'Through the looking glass: envisioning new library technologies" AI text generators as explained by ChatGPT', *Library Hi Tech News*. doi: 10.1108/LHTN-02-2023-0017.
 - 9) George Pallivathukal, R. et al. (2024) 'ChatGPT for Academic Purposes: Survey Among Undergraduate Healthcare Students in Malaysia', *Cureus*. doi: 10.7759/cureus.53032.
 - 10) Ho, P. X. P. (2024) 'Using ChatGPT in English Language Learning: A Study on I.T. Students' Attitudes, Habits, and Perceptions', *International Journal of TESOL & Education*, 4(1). doi: 10.54855/ijte.24414.
 - 11) Houston, A. B. and Corrado, E. M. (2023) 'Embracing ChatGPT: Implications of Emergent Language Models for Academia and Libraries', *Technical Services Quarterly*, 40(2). doi: 10.1080/07317131.2023.2187110.
 - 12) Inamdar, S. (2023) 'Impact of artificial intelligence text generators (AITGs) on libraries', *Library Hi Tech News*. doi: 10.1108/LHTN-03-2023-0048.
 - 13) Kendrick, C. (2022) *The Efficacy of ChatGPT: Is it Time for the Librarians to Go Home? The Scholarly Kitchen*. <https://share.google/Zmlw2swgOm0HVDiTo>
 - 14) Kirtania, D. K. (2023) 'OpenAIChatGPT for Library and Information Science (LIS) Professionals', *SSRN Electronic Journal*. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4404903.
 - 15) Kirtania, D. K. and Patra, S. K. (2023) 'Open Peer Review on QeiosOpenAIChatGPT enered Content and Similarity Index: A study of selected terms from the Library & Information Science (LIS)', *Qeios*, 70(June), pp. 1–10. doi: 10.56042/alis.v70i2.1189.
 - 16) Lappalainen, Y. and Narayanan, N. (2023) 'Aisha: A Custom AI Library Chatbot Using the ChatGPT API', *Journal of Web Librarianship*. doi: 10.1080/19322909.2023.2221477.
 - 17) Lund, B. D. and Wang, T. (2023) 'Chatting about ChatGPT: how may AI and GPT impact academia and libraries?', *Library Hi Tech News*. doi: 10.1108/LHTN-01-2023-0009.
 - 18) Mali, T. S. and Deshmukh, R. K. (2023) 'Use of Chat Gpt in Library Services', *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 11(4), pp. 264–266. Available at: www.ijcrt.org.
 - 19) Masa'deh, R. et al. (2024) 'Antecedents of adoption and usage of ChatGPT among Jordanian university students: Empirical study', *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 8(2). doi: 10.5267/j.ijdns.2023.11.024.
 - 20) *New Technology from Sage Report Explores Librarian Leadership in the Age of AI*. (n.d.). Retrieved October 10, 2025, from https://www.sagepub.com/explore-our-content/press-office/press-releases/2025/05/20/new-technology-from-sage-report-explores-librarian-leadership-in-the-age-of-ai?utm_source=chatgpt.com
 - 21) Nguyen, H. H., Vu, Q. N. and Vu, M. H. T. (2024) 'The Impact of Academic Integrity on the Intention to Use ChatGPT in the Studies of Students in Hanoi, Vietnam', *RESEARCH REVIEW International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 9(2). doi: 10.31305/rrijm.2024.v09.n02.022.
 - 22) Niloy, A. C. et al. (2024) 'Why do students use ChatGPT? Answering through a triangulation approach', *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 6. doi: 10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100208.
 - 23) Padhiyar, R. and Modha, S. (2024) 'Impact of the Usage of ChatGPT on Creativity Among Postgraduate Student', *International Journal of Sustainable Social Science (IJSSS)*, 2(1). doi: 10.59890/ijsss.v2i1.1376.
 - 24) Panda, S. and Kaur, N. (2023) 'Revolutionizing language processing in libraries with SheetGPT: an integration of Google Sheet and ChatGPT plugin', *Library Hi Tech News*. doi: 10.1108/LHTN-03-2023-0051.
 - 25) Pierre – Robertson, P. (2023) '#SuperLibrarian – the evolving role of librarians in technology

- spaces', *Digital Library Perspectives*. doi: 10.1108/DLP-04-2023-0026.
- 26) Pival, P. R. (2023) 'How to incorporate artificial intelligence (AI) into your library workflow', *Library Hi Tech News*. doi: 10.1108/LHTN-03-2023-0052.
- 27) Sabzalieva, Emma; Valentini, A. (2023) *ChatGPT and artificial intelligence in higher education: quick start guide | IIEP Unesco – Etico Platform on ethics and corruption in education, Paris, UNESCO*. Available at: <https://etico.iiep.unesco.org/en/chatgpt-artificial-intelligence-higher-education-quick-start-guide> (Accessed: 21 October 2024).
- 28) Salifu, I. *et al.* (2024) 'Economics students' behavioural intention and usage of ChatGPT in higher education: a hybrid structural equation modelling-artificial neural network approach', *Cogent Social Sciences*, 10(1). doi: 10.1080/23311886.2023.2300177.
- 29) Silvestre, A. S. S. *et al.* (2024) 'Students' perception about ChatGPT's impact on their Academic Education', in. doi: 10.5753/sbie.2023.234602.
- 30) Subaveerapandiyam, Vinoth, A. and Tiwary, N. (2023) 'Netizens, Academicians, and Information Professionals' Opinions About AI With Special Reference To ChatGPT', *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.07136v1>
- 31) Sun, D. *et al.* (2024) 'Would ChatGPT-facilitated programming mode impact college students' programming behaviors, performances, and perceptions? An empirical study', *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 21(1). doi: 10.1186/s41239-024-00446-5.
- 32) Valova, I., Mladenova, T. and Kanev, G. (2024) 'Students' Perception of ChatGPT Usage in Education', *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 15(1). doi: 10.14569/IJACSA.2024.0150143.
- 33) Verma, M. (2023) 'Novel Study on AI-Based Chatbot (ChatGPT) Impacts on the Traditional Library Management', *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 7(1), pp. 961–964. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368608640>.
- 34) Zhao, R. *et al.* (2023) 'Insights and Reflections of the Impact of ChatGPT on Intelligent Knowledge Services in Libraries', *Journal of Library and Information Science in Agriculture*, 35(1). doi: 10.13998/j.cnki.issn1002-1248.23-0116.